

EFFECTIVE USE OF SOCIAL MEDIA MARKETING SERVICES IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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Annotation. This article describes the scientific-based analysis of marketing services, their organization, ways and stages of effective use of social media marketing services in higher education muassasas as well as recommendations by the authors.

Keywords: higher education institution, marketing programs, higher education marketer, marketer, test, demo, creative copywriter, marketing strategies, target audience, attractiveness.

OLIJ TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA IJTIMOIJ MEDIA MARKETING XIZMATLARIDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISH

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada oliy ta'lim muassasalarida marketing xizmatlari, ularning tashkil etilishi, ijtimoiy media marketing xizmatlaridan samarali foydalanish yo'llari va bosqichlariga oid ilmiy asoslangan tahlillar hamda mualliflar tomonidan tavsiyalar bayon etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: oliy ta'lim muassasasi, marketing dasturlari, oliy ta'lim marketinggi, marketolog, sinov, demo, ijodiy kopirayter, marketing strategiyalari, maqsadli auditoriya, jozibadorlik.

Since higher education is a huge investment, students are required to think carefully about the right choice. Marketing programs in higher education must address these issues and present the institution as a unique environment.

Higher education marketing is a form of advertising aimed at 18- to 24-year-olds using effective new methods. Thus, good marketing efforts of an institution are based on careful planning and strategic research. We need to make a marketing plan for the

students of the institution because it would be appropriate if the big problems they face are solved.

One of the challenges that institutions and universities constantly face is marketing their programs in an effective and visible way. Creating a user-friendly and user-friendly website should be the first step in your strategy.

Explanations for each program should be clear and concise for students to read. Based on this, you can strategically promote your programs on your blog, social media, email, and other channels available to you.

A marketer studies how products and services are branded and marketed to a target market made up of specific demographic groups.

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Using data-driven market intelligence, institutions can increase their brand awareness and image, attract potential students, and make them more loyal.

Both for-profit and for-profit businesses hire marketing professionals. Most marketers go on to work in brand management, market analysis, advertising, public relations, sales, or customer service. In this process, the use of SMM is of particular importance.

SMM strategy allows you to understand how to reach the largest audience. With its help, tactics for brand recognition and attracting subscribers are built. This is one of the most important points in the plan. To compare indicators, you need to understand what performance parameters you need to monitor in the work of the team. Based on the results of the analysis, if necessary, a decision is made to correct the work plan or to continue the work in the same direction.[1]

An SMM strategy often takes the form of a presentation. Each step is on a separate slide for ease of understanding information. Sometimes it is created in PDF format for ease of viewing on different devices.

It is advisable to use the following SMM marketing strategies in higher educational institutions.[2]

1. Use of trial and demo data.[3]

Institutional students love free stuff. Therefore, in the implementation of marketing research in higher education institutions, applicants are offered master classes in their fields of interest (free of charge), familiarization with the possibilities of higher education in a free environment, free meals, libraries, it would be appropriate if the opportunity to participate in laboratory training was established.

2. Using a creative copywriting system.

LSI copywriting is a type of copywriting based on the use of LSI keywords. This helps the text look natural and improves search engine optimization.

Commercial copywriting is writing texts to advertise goods or services. The main goal of such a copywriter is to attract customers and increase sales.

Informational copywriting is writing texts designed to inform customers about a particular product or service.

Direct response copywriting is writing texts that contain a clear call to action.

Creative copywriting is writing texts that are unique and creative. Such texts can be used to promote a brand or product.

Image copywriting is writing texts that create a positive image of a company or product.[4]

3. Using proven strategies.[5]

Higher education marketing comes with its own set of challenges. There are a number of strategies for solving these problems.

Marketing strategies used in solving problems in higher education.

In the process of research, we have studied a number of stages of attracting students using social media marketing in higher education institutions. If we implement these steps in the higher education system, we will eliminate some problems and increase the flow of students.

Stage 1. Organization of target audience.

One of the main business goals of any university or institute is to attract "talented and quality" students to the higher education institution. To do this, it is necessary to create a target audience in social networks and identify responsible students for higher education institutions.

Stage 2. Using content marketing techniques.

Publishing positive and interesting articles on the activities and services of higher education institutions in an online magazine or newspaper, using the services of bloggers who provide free information on important topics for students and environmental events.

Stage 3. Using the services of marketers.

Marketers working in the field of higher education visit neighborhoods, districts, and regions to explain positive opinions about the institution to applicants interested in this field and their parents.

It would be appropriate if the results of the research conducted by marketers during the educational process were shown to the applicants and their parents online and offline.

Step 4. Higher education institutions offer price discounts to applicants.

In this process, it would be appropriate if the contract prices for entering the university's educational fields were cheaper than other universities, the allocation of high-quality benefits, and the accommodation costs for certain types of students were covered at the university's expense.

Step 5. Effective use of the services of foreign partners in order to increase the attractiveness of higher education institutions.

In this direction, the institution will again use the services of marketers to find ways to attract foreign investors, use social networks to invite foreign teachers to teach, and use their pedagogical talents to attract students.

Step 6. Introduction of banking services in an educational institution.

In order to create convenience for students, higher education institutions will strengthen relations with commercial banks and introduce banking services in educational institutions for efficient use of time. It would be appropriate to introduce banking services in a higher education institution in order to reduce the time of obtaining educational loans, making contract payments, and making payments for dormitory services and accommodation.

Step 7. Effective use of the services of foreign partners to increase the facilities for students at the higher education institution.

It would be expedient to identify the highly talented part of students and organize free trips, vacations and internships to partner foreign countries to increase the attractiveness of higher education institutions.

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